

Multimodal Transformers for CGM and Diet Based Glucose Forecasting

Jung Lee¹, Suheng Yao¹, Nicole Spartano², Maura Walker², Xiaowei
Yu³, Lin Tang¹, and Huimin Cheng^{*1}

¹Department of Biostatistics, Boston University, Boston, MA, USA

²Department of Medicine, Boston University, Boston, MA, USA

³Department of Computer Science, Missouri University of Science and
Technology, Rolla, MO, USA

*Corresponding author: Huimin Cheng, huimin23@bu.edu

March 10, 2026

Abstract

Continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) enables personalized metabolic health support, but forecasting glucose in free-living settings is difficult because future trajectories depend on both endogenous dynamics and sparsely recorded meals. We developed MealRes-Gate, a multimodal transformer that treats meal information as a gated residual refinement to a strong CGM-based backbone. In non-diabetic and pre-diabetic adults from the Framingham Heart Study, MealRes-Gate consistently outperformed recurrent, Transformer-based, and GluFormer baselines across 30-, 60-, 90-, and 120-minute horizons. Gains were largest in postprandial, hyperglycemic, and hypoglycemic windows, and extended to clinically relevant postprandial summaries including peak glucose, area under the

curve, and glucose range. Ablation analysis showed that engineered CGM features provided the dominant predictive backbone, while explicit meal features contributed smaller but meaningful gains when integrated through the proposed residual-gating mechanism. These results show that sparse dietary information can improve glucose forecasting without destabilizing prediction when incorporated selectively.

1 Introduction

The increasing use of continuous glucose monitors (CGMs) in non-clinical populations has enabled a new class of digital health applications aimed at metabolic optimization and early disease prevention in non-diabetic and prediabetic individuals [54, 26, 3, 15, 18, 44]. These applications range from personalized meal guidance and exercise timing recommendations to broader real-time support for metabolic health monitoring. Despite their diversity, they rely on the same core capability: accurate forecasting of an individual’s glucose trajectory over the next 30 minutes to 2 hours [40, 21, 8]. Such forecasting is the computational basis for actionable guidance. For example, a system may use short-term glucose prediction to anticipate an impending excursion, evaluate the likely effect of a behavioral choice, or support timely recommendations about meals, activity, or daily routines [34, 1, 9, 45, 51]. Thus, multi-horizon glucose forecasting is not merely a predictive task; it is a foundational capability for personalized, real-time metabolic intervention.

Despite this promise, forecasting glucose in non-diabetic individuals poses distinct challenges. CGM data are densely and passively collected, providing a high-resolution record of glucose dynamics over time. At short horizons, recent glucose history is often strongly predictive. At longer horizons, however, forecasting becomes increasingly difficult because future glucose is driven not only by endogenous temporal dynamics but also by exogenous behavioral perturbations, especially meals [3, 31, 10, 45, 16]. In non-diabetic populations, meals are a major source of acute glucose excursions, and

their effects can persist for several hours [14, 3, 10, 12, 16].

Yet meal information is precisely the modality that is least reliably observed in free-living settings. Unlike CGM, which is recorded automatically, dietary intake is typically self-reported and therefore sparse, incomplete, and heterogeneous across participants [42, 7, 33, 58, 5]. This problem is especially severe in non-diabetic populations, where there is little clinical incentive to log meals consistently; by contrast, in type 1 diabetes, for instance, meal information is more often recorded because it is integral to insulin dosing and decision support [18, 25, 43]. This mismatch between densely observed CGM trajectories and sparsely observed meal records creates a key challenge for multimodal forecasting: meal information may be highly informative when available, but models cannot assume that it will be present [54, 26, 3, 45].

Existing approaches do not fully address this setting. Prior work on glucose forecasting has explored classical autoregressive and related time-series methods [37, 34, 50, 48], early neural network and conventional machine learning approaches [29, 13], deep recurrent neural networks [20, 57, 28, 32], more recent Transformer-based architectures [19, 35, 4, 49, 56, 22, 23], and diabetes-focused models that explicitly incorporate meal and insulin information [53, 41, 52, 20, 32]. However, most meal-augmented approaches have been developed in diabetes cohorts where meal logging is relatively complete because it is tied to insulin management [52, 39, 30]. Standard multimodal fusion strategies often assume modality-complete inputs, or are designed for more limited missing-modality settings rather than extreme and systematic missingness in one channel [2, 24, 55, 46, 17, 47]. When dietary data are overwhelmingly missing, such approaches may generalize poorly, especially when the modality patterns seen at inference differ from those observed during training [24, 55, 46, 47]. What is needed instead is a forecasting framework in which meal information acts as an optional refinement: useful when present, but never required. What is needed instead is a forecasting framework in which meal information acts as an optional refinement: useful when present, but never required.

In this work, we study multi-horizon glucose forecasting in a free-living cohort of 1,546 non-diabetic adults using CGM and diet information under severe meal-data missingness. We benchmark a diverse set of forecasting approaches, including recurrent models LSTM [20, 32], Transformer architectures [19, 35, 49], and a CGM foundation model GluFormer [23], across 30-, 60-, 90-, and 120-minute prediction horizons under both temporal and patient-held-out evaluation protocols. Our analysis yields two main findings.

First, we show that domain-informed engineered features, including MAGE [36], power spectral density [11], rates of change [6], consistently outperform raw CGM inputs. The mechanism is straightforward: while meals are an exogenous input to the glucose system, the glucose trace itself is the physiological output. Engineered features derived from this trace therefore encode the consequences of dietary perturbations, without requiring knowledge of the meal itself. We confirm this empirically: a classifier trained solely on these CGM-derived features detects meal events with an AUC of 0.70 (details in Supplementary Section B), demonstrating that the glucose response carries a readable signature of its dietary cause. This explains why engineered features provide a strong forecasting backbone even when meal records are entirely absent.

Second, we introduce MealRes-Gate, a residual gating architecture that builds on this backbone by incorporating explicit dietary information, when available, as a structurally isolated, zero-initialized, per-horizon correction. An implicit meal detector inferred from CGM patterns activates this correction even for participants with no dietary records, while the residual design guarantees that meal data can only refine, never corrupt, the underlying prediction. Together, these contributions establish a framework for robust glucose forecasting under the severe dietary data missingness that characterizes real-world non-diabetic CGM deployment, the population where accurate forecasting has the greatest preventive potential.

2 Results

2.1 Datasets

We used CGM data from the Framingham Heart Study (FHS), a multigenerational, community-based cohort with extensive phenotypic and clinical characterization. Detailed descriptions of the FHS design and participating cohorts have been reported previously [38]. For the present analysis, we considered participants from the Third Generation, New Offspring, and Omni cohorts who attended the first year of their fourth examination cycle between September 2022 and July 2025.

Under this protocol, participants wore a Dexcom G6 Pro CGM device on the upper arm or abdomen for up to 10 days under free-living conditions, with interstitial glucose recorded every 5 minutes. During the same monitoring window, dietary intake was assessed using the Automated Self-Administered 24-Hour Recall (ASA24), a validated web-based dietary assessment system developed by the National Cancer Institute [27]. Participants were asked to complete two weekday recalls and one weekend recall, and reported meal events were mapped to the nearest 5-minute CGM interval to align dietary information with the glucose time series. As illustrated in Figure 1a,b, this process produced an asymmetric multimodal dataset characterized by densely and passively collected CGM trajectories paired with substantially sparser, intermittently recorded meal information.

2.2 Method Overview

MealRes-Gate is a transformer-based architecture for multi-horizon glucose forecasting designed for free-living data with dense CGM measurements but sparse and incomplete meal records. We first partition each continuous CGM trajectory into consecutive 30-minute windows, each containing six 5-minute glucose measurements (Figure 1c). For every window, we compute CGM features that summarize local glucose dynamics, including level, trend, and variability; the full feature specification is provided in

Supplementary Section A.2. Meal records are aligned to the same 30-minute grid. A window is labeled meal-positive if at least one eating event occurs within that interval, and when multiple eating events fall in the same window, their nutritional quantities are summed to form a single aggregated meal representation. Each meal window is then encoded using 17 nutritional and meal timing features, including carbohydrate, protein, sugar, fat, whole grain, and refined grain. These aligned CGM and meal representations are embedded separately and passed to MealRes-Gate.

A key design principle of MealRes-Gate is that CGM should remain the dominant forecasting signal, while meal information should act only as an auxiliary refinement. Accordingly, rather than directly concatenating meal embeddings with glucose embeddings, the model keeps the dietary pathway separate and introduces it through a residual correction branch (Figure 1d). Specifically, CGM embeddings are processed by a Transformer backbone to generate a baseline glucose forecast, whereas meal embeddings enter through a separate cross-attention pathway that interacts with the latent CGM representation without replacing the main CGM stream.

Because meal logs are incomplete in free-living settings, explicit meal indicators alone are insufficient for determining when the dietary pathway should be activated. To address this, we augment the meal branch with an implicit meal-probability signal. Specifically, we pre-train a logistic regression model on CGM-derived features to estimate $P(\text{meal} \mid \text{CGM})$ for each 30-minute window (details in Supplementary Section B). When an explicit meal log is present, the model uses that information directly; otherwise, it falls back on the CGM-inferred meal probability. This signal is then combined with contextual meal-related variables, including time since last meal and recent carbohydrate intake, to form a horizon-specific gate that assigns a separate weight to the meal branch at the 30-, 60-, 90-, and 120-minute horizons, thereby controlling how strongly the meal pathway modifies the CGM-only prediction at each horizon.

The resulting meal correction is added to the baseline CGM forecast as a residual

adjustment, yielding the final prediction. Thus, MealRes-Gate preserves a strong CGM forecasting backbone while allowing dietary information to contribute selectively when informative, especially at longer horizons where meal effects are more likely to emerge and CGM-only forecasts become less reliable. The model outputs glucose forecasts at 30-, 60-, 90-, and 120-minute horizons (Figure 1e), which can support downstream applications such as meal guidance, timing recommendations, and preventive metabolic monitoring (Figure 1f).

2.3 MealRes-Gate Improves Multi-horizon Glucose Forecasting

We first evaluated MealRes-Gate in the setting where future glucose is predicted for participants whose historical records are already available. For each participant, we applied a chronological split of the longitudinal data into Training (60%), Validation (20%), and Test (20%) segments, so that model fitting and hyperparameter tuning used only earlier observations and all reported results were obtained on a held-out future segment. Forecasting was formulated as a sliding-window task: at each eligible anchor time t , the model consumed the preceding 6 hours of CGM data and predicted glucose over the subsequent horizon. We considered four prediction horizons—30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes—and evaluated performance using mean absolute error (MAE). We compared MealRes-Gate against a diverse set of baselines, including recurrent and Transformer-based models trained on raw CGM input, as well as GluFormer models [] with and without explicit meal information.

To assess performance in physiologically meaningful settings, we further stratified the held-out test windows into clinically relevant subgroups. Figure 2 summarizes results for 3,790 postprandial windows, 101,372 non-postprandial windows, 1,079 hyperglycemic windows, and 109 hypoglycemic windows, contributed by 210, 1,546, 199, and 16 participants, respectively. Postprandial windows were defined as anchor times within 2 hours after a logged meal, whereas non-postprandial windows comprised all remaining eligible

Figure 1: **Free-living multimodal data collection and MealRes-Gate workflow.**

a. In the FHS free-living setting, CGM was collected continuously whereas dietary intake was recorded intermittently. **b.** Dense glucose trajectories and sparse meal logs with heterogeneous macronutrient composition. **c.** CGM and meal records were aligned into 30-minute windows and converted into CGM embeddings and meal embeddings. **d.** MealRes-Gate uses a Transformer CGM backbone to generate a baseline forecast and an auxiliary meal branch with cross-attention, meal detection, and horizon-specific gating to produce a residual meal correction. **e.** The model predicts glucose at 30-, 60-, 90-, and 120-minute horizons. **f.** Forecasts may support meal guidance, timing recommendations, and preventive metabolic monitoring.

Figure 2: Forecasting performance across clinically relevant subgroups. MAE at 30-, 60-, 90-, and 120-minute prediction horizons for MealRes-Gate and competing methods in (a) postprandial windows, (b) non-postprandial windows, (c) hyperglycemic windows (> 180 mg/dL), and (d) hypoglycemic windows (< 70 mg/dL). Lower MAE indicates better forecasting accuracy.

windows. Hyperglycemic and hypoglycemic windows were defined using thresholds of > 180 mg/dL and < 70 mg/dL, respectively. Because these strata differ substantially in prevalence, especially for the rarer hypo- and hyperglycemic regimes, the subgroup analysis provides a more informative test of model robustness than aggregate performance alone.

Across all four panels of Figure 2, forecasting error increased with prediction horizon for every method, as expected. MealRes-Gate nevertheless achieved the strongest and most consistent performance overall, and notably, its advantage generally grew with prediction horizon. This pattern suggests that the proposed architecture is particularly

effective when longer-range forecasting requires the model to preserve information about both recent glucose dynamics and delayed physiological effects.

The contrast between postprandial and non-postprandial windows further illustrates the difficulty of forecasting under different physiological states (Figure 2a–b). Errors were uniformly higher in postprandial windows than in non-postprandial windows at the same horizon, indicating that meal-related glucose dynamics are intrinsically harder to predict. After meals, glucose trajectories are affected not only by recent CGM history, but also by the timing, quantity, and composition of food intake, as well as person-specific metabolic responses. Correspondingly, prediction error in postprandial windows rose sharply between 30 and 60 minutes and then increased more gradually thereafter, whereas non-postprandial windows showed a steadier and more linear degradation in accuracy. Even in the non-postprandial setting, however, MealRes-Gate remained the top-performing model, indicating that its benefit is not limited to explicitly meal-related windows.

The most pronounced gains appeared in hyperglycemic and hypoglycemic windows (Figure 2c–d), which are also the most challenging subgroups to forecast. Hyperglycemic windows (panel c) produced the highest absolute errors across all models, with MAEs exceeding 50–60 mg/dL at the longest horizons, while hypoglycemic windows (panel d) reached approximately 30–38 mg/dL at 120 minutes. This difficulty stems from two complementary sources. First, because the cohort consisted primarily of non-diabetic and pre-diabetic individuals, episodes of frank hyperglycemia and hypoglycemia were relatively rare, leaving fewer training examples for models to learn these regimes. Second, glucose trajectories in both extreme states are often rapid, nonlinear, and influenced by factors not directly captured in the available inputs, including stress, physical activity, sleep, and hormonal fluctuations. As a result, these windows are harder to predict from CGM history and sparse meal records alone. Despite these challenges, MealRes-Gate showed the strongest separation from competing methods precisely in these rare and difficult settings, with its advantage remaining substantial at 90 and 120

minutes.

2.4 Ablation Study

To identify which components of MealRes-Gate are responsible for the observed gains, we conducted a structured ablation study across the same four strata used in the main evaluation: postprandial, non-postprandial, hyperglycemic, and hypoglycemic windows (Table 1). Starting from the full model, we removed one component at a time. Specifically, we replaced the smart-zone loss with standard mean squared error (MSE), replaced the soft residual meal correction with naive concatenation-based fusion, removed food features entirely, and finally replaced the engineered CGM representation with raw CGM input. Several conclusions emerge from Table 1.

Clinically aware loss sharpens extreme-regime accuracy. Comparing MealRes-Gate with AB1 shows that the smart-zone loss contributes beyond architecture alone. Replacing it with standard MSE generally worsened performance across all strata, with the clearest degradation in hyperglycemic and hypoglycemic windows. For example, in hyperglycemic windows, MAE increased from 12.97 to 15.31 mg/dL at T+30 and from 38.72 to 42.07 mg/dL at T+60 when the smart-zone loss was replaced by MSE. By contrast, the effect in postprandial and non-postprandial windows was smaller. These results suggest that the smart-zone loss preferentially improves accuracy in rare, clinically important extreme-glucose regimes, rather than merely optimizing average fit.

Meal input improves performance only when integrated effectively. The comparison between MealRes-Gate, AB2, and AB3 shows that meal information is most effective when introduced through the proposed gated residual pathway. AB3, which replaces the soft residual correction with naive concatenation-based fusion, consistently worsened performance relative to the full model across nearly all strata, indicating that the benefit of meal input depends on how it is incorporated rather than on simply adding more variables. AB2, which removes the per-horizon gating mechanism, had a smaller

overall effect, but its degradation was more visible in difficult regimes, particularly hyperglycemic windows, and at longer horizons. For example, in hyperglycemic windows, MAE increased from 12.97 to 14.89 mg/dL at T+30 and from 38.72 to 42.07 mg/dL at T+60 in AB2, while AB3 yielded 15.49 and 40.21 mg/dL, respectively. Together, these results suggest that the soft residual design provides the main protection against noisy meal fusion, whereas the gating module further refines when meal information should influence prediction across horizons.

Engineered CGM features are the dominant source of gain. Replacing engineered features with raw CGM input (AB5 in Table 1) consistently caused the largest degradation in performance. This effect was modest but persistent in postprandial and non-postprandial windows, and became especially pronounced in hyperglycemic and hypoglycemic regimes. For example, in hyperglycemic windows at T+120, the full model achieved an MAE of 53.3 mg/dL, whereas the raw-CGM variant increased to 62.0 mg/dL; similarly, in hypoglycemic windows at T+120, MAE rose from 29.22 to 33.31 mg/dL. By contrast, removing food features entirely (AB4) led to only a modest degradation. This pattern suggests that the engineered CGM representation provides the primary predictive signal, whereas explicit food features contribute a smaller additional gain. The major reason is that CGM features reflect the body’s downstream response to meals, while logged meal variables represent the upstream input itself. Supplementary Section B shows that a logistic regression model trained only on CGM features achieved an AUC of 0.73 (Figure 8) for detecting whether a window occurred within the past 30 minutes of a meal. Together, these results suggest that much of the meal-related predictive signal is already embedded in the physiological patterns captured by the CGM features, with explicit food features serving mainly as a secondary refinement.

Table 1: Ablation study of MealRes-Gate components across clinically relevant glucose regimes. Each row progressively removes one component from the full model. All models use seed 12. Bold indicates best performance per column.

Model variant	T+30	T+60	T+90	T+120
<i>(a) Postprandial</i>				
MealRes-Gate (full)	8.11	13.70	14.21	14.36
AB1: – Smart zone loss (MSE only)	8.16	13.77	14.31	14.54
AB2: – P(meal) gating	8.02	13.52	14.16	14.42
AB3: – Soft residual (concat only)	8.18	13.69	14.30	14.59
AB4: – Food features entirely	8.26	13.81	14.43	14.69
AB5: – Engineered features (Raw CGM)	8.35	14.10	14.90	15.25
<i>(b) Non-postprandial</i>				
MealRes-Gate (full)	6.46	10.91	11.95	12.43
AB1: – Smart zone loss (MSE only)	6.69	11.18	12.27	12.75
AB2: – P(meal) gating	6.48	10.89	11.98	12.46
AB3: – Soft residual (concat only)	6.58	11.11	12.14	12.64
AB4: – Food features entirely	6.74	11.20	12.23	12.76
AB5: – Engineered features (Raw CGM)	6.84	11.36	12.66	13.38
<i>(c) Hyperglycemia (>180 mg/dL)</i>				
MealRes-Gate (full)	15.50	35.62	43.09	46.28
AB1: – Smart zone loss (MSE only)	16.57	37.26	42.63	43.79
AB2: – P(meal) gating	16.55	37.89	44.08	47.17
AB3: – Soft residual (concat only)	16.65	35.98	42.53	45.77
AB4: – Food features entirely	17.48	36.89	43.21	46.01
AB5: – Engineered features (Raw CGM)	17.19	40.67	49.10	53.15
<i>(d) Hypoglycemia (<70 mg/dL)</i>				
MealRes-Gate (full)	11.56	21.07	23.49	24.97
AB1: – Smart zone loss (MSE only)	12.23	22.92	24.88	25.87
AB2: – P(meal) gating	11.62	21.03	23.92	24.92
AB3: – Soft residual (concat only)	12.48	21.46	23.53	25.44
AB4: – Food features entirely	12.06	23.00	25.38	27.29
AB5: – Engineered features (Raw CGM)	13.64	23.43	26.28	28.34

2.5 Subgroup Analysis

To assess robustness across participant subgroups, we stratified forecasting performance by demographic and clinical characteristics, including sex, age, BMI, HbA1c, fasting glucose, and glucose coefficient of variation (CV) (Figure 3). Across all strata, MAE increased monotonically with prediction horizon, consistent with the greater uncertainty associated with longer-range glucose forecasting. Importantly, the overall pattern of performance remained stable across subgroups, suggesting that MealRes-Gate does not

rely on a narrow subset of participants to achieve strong average performance.

Differences across demographic factors were comparatively modest. The sex-, age-, and BMI-stratified panels showed broadly overlapping error distributions, with only small shifts in central tendency relative to the overall increase in error from T+30 to T+120. This pattern suggests that the model is reasonably robust across these participant characteristics and does not exhibit a strong performance drop in any single demographic subgroup.

In contrast, larger differences emerged when participants were stratified by metabolic status. Individuals with elevated HbA1c, impaired fasting glucose, and higher glucose CV tended to show systematically higher MAE, particularly at longer horizons. These subgroups likely represent participants with greater glycemic instability and more complex glucose dynamics, making future trajectories harder to predict even with multimodal input. Thus, the subgroup analysis suggests that residual prediction difficulty is driven more by metabolic heterogeneity than by demographic characteristics alone.

Among the clinical stratifications, glucose CV showed one of the clearest separations, with the high-variability subgroup exhibiting consistently worse performance than the low-variability subgroup. This is expected, as greater within-person glucose volatility reduces short-term predictability and amplifies uncertainty at longer horizons. Similar, though somewhat smaller, trends were observed for HbA1c and fasting glucose, indicating that chronic and acute markers of dysregulation both contribute to forecasting difficulty.

Overall, Figure 3 supports two main conclusions. First, MealRes-Gate remains broadly stable across demographic subgroups, which is important for equitable deployment. Second, the participants for whom forecasting remains most difficult are those with more dysregulated and variable glucose profiles, rather than those defined by age, sex, or BMI alone. These findings suggest that future gains are likely to come less from demographic tailoring and more from better modeling of high-variability metabolic

states.

Figure 3: Subgroup analysis of forecasting performance across demographic and clinical strata. Distribution of MAE for MealRes-Gate across 30-, 60-, 90-, and 120-minute prediction horizons, stratified by sex, age, BMI, HbA1c, fasting glucose, and glucose coefficient of variation (CV). Significance markers indicate pairwise subgroup comparisons at each horizon.

2.6 Model Explanations and Feature Importance

To interpret what drives prediction in MealRes-Gate, we quantified the importance of engineered CGM features at short and long horizons using permutation analysis (Figure 4). Feature importance was defined as the percentage increase in MAE after permuting a given feature while holding all others fixed.

Feature importance shifted markedly with forecasting horizon. At T+30 (Figure 4a), prediction was driven mainly by current glucose and immediate local dynamics, including the 24-hour mean, 5-minute change, current glucose, window minimum, and glucose 10 minutes earlier. This indicates that short-horizon forecasting depends primarily on

the current state of the trajectory and its recent direction of change.

At T+120 (Figure 4b), the ranking changed substantially. The 24-hour mean became the dominant predictor, followed by broader historical summaries such as EWMA and mean features over 6–24 hour windows, as well as time-of-day information. Thus, long-horizon prediction relied less on immediate local fluctuations and more on slower background structure, including recent glycemic baseline, accumulated trend, and circadian context.

Several additional observations are noteworthy. First, the 24-hour mean is highly influential at both horizons, indicating that recent baseline glycemic state provides a stable anchor for prediction across timescales. Second, rate-of-change features are most valuable at T+30 but are largely replaced by longer-window summaries at T+120, consistent with the idea that short-term momentum is informative only over limited horizons. Third, time-of-day enters the top features only at the longer horizon, suggesting that circadian structure becomes more relevant when projecting farther into the future.

Figure 4: Feature importance of engineered CGM predictors at short- and long-horizon forecasting.

2.7 Forecasting Clinically Relevant Postprandial Metrics

We next asked whether improved glucose forecasting translates into more accurate prediction of clinically relevant postprandial summaries. We therefore evaluated four derived outcomes from the predicted trajectories: peak glucose, time-to-peak, area under the glucose curve (AUC), and glucose range (Figure 5).

Across all four outcomes, error increased with prediction horizon for every method, but MealRes-Gate consistently achieved the lowest or near-lowest MAE. The clearest gains were observed for peak glucose, AUC, and glucose range, particularly at longer horizons, indicating that improved trajectory forecasting yields more accurate estimates of excursion magnitude, cumulative burden, and variability.

By contrast, the separation between methods was smaller for time-to-peak, which is more sensitive to small shifts in the predicted location of the maximum. Overall, these results show that the advantage of MealRes-Gate extends beyond pointwise glucose prediction to clinically interpretable summaries of postprandial response.

Figure 5: MAE for four derived clinical outcomes—postprandial peak glucose, time-to-peak, area under the glucose curve (AUC), and glucose range—computed from predicted trajectories at 30-, 60-, 90-, and 120-minute horizons.

2.8 Generalization to Unseen Participants

The evaluations in the preceding subsections address a within-participant forecasting setting: for each individual, earlier observations are used for training and later observations are used for testing. This design is appropriate for assessing prospective prediction over time, but it does not answer a distinct and practically important question:

whether the model can generalize to *new individuals* whose data were never observed during training. In CGM-based digital health applications, this distinction is critical. A model may perform well when it can learn participant-specific baselines, rhythms, and response patterns from historical data, yet degrade substantially when deployed to a previously unseen person with different metabolic dynamics, meal-reporting behavior, and glucose variability. Evaluating generalization to unseen participants is therefore necessary to determine whether the model captures transferable physiological structure rather than relying primarily on person-specific memorization. To assess generalization, we performed 5-fold patient-held-out cross-validation. In each fold, we trained the model on 80% of participants and evaluated it on the remaining 20%, ensuring that no participant appeared in both training and test sets.

Figure 2 shows that MealRes-Gate maintains the same overall performance hierarchy observed in the chronological time-window evaluation. Across all prediction horizons and all clinical subgroups, MealRes-Gate achieves the lowest MAE among the compared methods, indicating that its gains are not merely an artifact of repeated exposure to the same participants. In postprandial windows (Fig. 2a), MealRes-Gate reaches 13.77 mg/dL at T+120 min, compared with 14.87–15.24 mg/dL for the baselines, corresponding to a 7–10% reduction in error. A similar pattern is observed in non-postprandial windows (Fig. 2b), where MealRes-Gate achieves 12.44 mg/dL at T+120 min and outperforms the next-best method, LSTM-CGM, by 8.9%.

As shown in Figure 6, MealRes-Gate achieves the lowest MAE at every horizon and in every clinical subgroup. In postprandial windows (Figure 6a), MealRes-Gate reaches 13.77 mg/dL at T+120 min, compared to 14.87–15.24 mg/dL for all baselines — a 7–10% reduction in forecasting error. A comparable gap persists in non-postprandial windows (Figure 6b), where MealRes-Gate (12.44 mg/dL at T+120) outperforms the next-best method, LSTM-CGM (13.65 mg/dL), by 8.9%.

The advantage is most pronounced in clinically critical regimes. For hyperglycemic

windows (Figure 6c), MealRes-Gate achieves 55.58 mg/dL at T+120 versus 61.91–64.19 mg/dL for baselines, an absolute reduction of 6–9 mg/dL. In hypoglycemic windows (Figure 6d), MealRes-Gate (28.53 mg/dL) outperforms all competitors (34.56–36.26 mg/dL) by 17–21%. The shaded bands, representing ± 1 standard deviation across folds, further show that MealRes-Gate exhibits the lowest cross-fold variability, indicating stable generalization regardless of which participants are held out.

Figure 6: Generalization to unseen participants under 5-fold patient-held-out cross-validation in (a) postprandial windows, (b) non-postprandial windows, (c) hyperglycemic windows (> 180 mg/dL), and (d) hypoglycemic windows (< 70 mg/dL). Shaded bands indicate ± 1 standard deviation across the five folds. Lower MAE indicates better forecasting accuracy.

3 Discussion

In this study, we developed MealRes-Gate, a multimodal forecasting architecture for free-living glucose prediction that combines engineered CGM features with sparse meal information through a gated residual design. Across all evaluated horizons, MealRes-Gate consistently outperformed recurrent, Transformer-based, and prior GluFormer baselines, with the clearest gains emerging in physiologically difficult settings, including postprandial, hyperglycemic, and hypoglycemic windows. These findings suggest that dietary information can improve glucose forecasting, but only when incorporated in a way that preserves CGM as the dominant predictive backbone and prevents sparse meal records from introducing instability.

A central observation of this work is that glucose forecasting difficulty is highly state dependent. Errors were systematically higher in postprandial than in non-postprandial windows, and highest in hyperglycemic and hypoglycemic regimes, indicating that extreme and meal-perturbed glucose trajectories remain the most challenging settings for all methods. These regimes are difficult not only because they are rarer in our cohort, which consisted primarily of non-diabetic and pre-diabetic individuals, but also because they are intrinsically more heterogeneous and may depend on factors not directly captured in the available inputs, including stress, physical activity, sleep, and other latent physiological states. Against this more difficult background, the stronger performance of MealRes-Gate suggests that its benefit lies less in improving already stable trajectories and more in increasing robustness under rapid, nonlinear, and underrepresented glucose dynamics.

The ablation results help clarify why the model works. Engineered CGM features provided the dominant source of predictive gain: replacing them with raw CGM input caused the largest degradation across all clinical strata, especially in extreme-glucose regimes. This indicates that carefully constructed summaries of level, trend, variability, and longer-term glucose history remain highly effective for this forecasting problem. At

the same time, explicit food features still provided a meaningful but smaller benefit. Removing food features entirely produced only modest degradation overall, consistent with the finding that engineered CGM features already encode part of the downstream physiological response to meals. Indeed, CGM-derived features alone were sufficient to detect recent meal activity with reasonable accuracy in supplementary analyses, suggesting that much of the meal-related signal is already embedded in the glucose trajectory itself. Explicit food information therefore appears to function mainly as a selective refinement, rather than as a dominant second modality.

Equally important is how meal information is incorporated. Naive fusion degraded performance relative to the proposed residual design, and removing the horizon-specific gating mechanism reduced performance in several harder settings. These findings support the central architectural principle of MealRes-Gate: meal input should not be fused indiscriminately with CGM representations, but instead should enter as a guarded residual correction whose influence varies across prediction horizons. This is especially relevant in free-living data, where meal logs are incomplete and noisy. Under such conditions, a model that treats meal information as uniformly trustworthy risks overfitting to missingness and reporting error, whereas a residual-gated design can exploit dietary information when informative while defaulting to the stronger CGM backbone otherwise.

Beyond pointwise glucose prediction, MealRes-Gate also improved forecasting of clinically relevant postprandial summary measures, including peak glucose, AUC, and glucose range. This is an important result because the practical value of glucose forecasting lies not only in predicting individual future values, but also in supporting downstream interpretation of excursion magnitude, cumulative burden, and response severity. The model further generalized well to unseen participants under patient-held-out evaluation, indicating that its gains are not solely due to repeated exposure to the same individuals over time. Together, these findings suggest that the proposed architecture captures structure that transfers across both physiological regimes and participants,

strengthening its relevance for real-world deployment.

Several limitations should be noted. First, the cohort consisted primarily of non-diabetic and pre-diabetic participants, so hyperglycemic and hypoglycemic windows were relatively rare. While this makes the strong performance in these regimes encouraging, it also limits the precision with which conclusions can be drawn for more severe dysglycemia. Second, meal records were self-reported and therefore incomplete and potentially noisy, which motivated the implicit meal-probability component but also constrains how precisely meal effects can be learned. Third, the model used only CGM and meal features; other behavioral and physiological signals, such as physical activity, sleep, medication, and stress, were not available but may explain part of the residual error, especially in extreme-glucose regimes. Finally, although engineered features performed strongly here, the relative value of feature engineering versus representation learning may differ in cohorts with denser multimodal sensing or more severe metabolic dysregulation.

These limitations point naturally to future work. One direction is to extend MealResGate to incorporate additional contextual signals, including activity, sleep, and wearable-derived physiological markers, to better explain glucose excursions not attributable to meals alone. A second is to evaluate the model in cohorts with type 2 diabetes or broader metabolic heterogeneity, where both the prevalence and dynamics of extreme glucose events may differ substantially. A third is to investigate whether the implicit meal-probability mechanism can be improved through weak supervision or semi-supervised learning while remaining subordinate to the main forecasting objective. More broadly, our results suggest that robust multimodal glucose forecasting in free-living settings requires not only richer inputs, but also architectures that explicitly account for missingness, uneven modality quality, and the asymmetric value of contextual information across prediction horizons.

Overall, this work shows that sparse dietary information can be made useful for glu-

cose forecasting without allowing it to destabilize prediction. By combining a strong engineered CGM backbone with residual, horizon-specific meal refinement, MealResGate improves forecasting across clinically relevant regimes and extends naturally to downstream postprandial metrics. These findings highlight a broader principle for multimodal health modeling in free-living environments: auxiliary modalities are most valuable when integrated selectively, in a way that respects both their informativeness and their unreliability.

References

- [1] David J Albers, Matthew Levine, Bruce Gluckman, Henry Ginsberg, George Hripisak, and Lena Mamykina. Personalized glucose forecasting for type 2 diabetes using data assimilation. *PLoS computational biology*, 13(4):e1005232, 2017.
- [2] Tadas Baltrušaitis, Chaitanya Ahuja, and Louis-Philippe Morency. Multimodal machine learning: A survey and taxonomy. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 41(2):423–443, 2018.
- [3] Sarah E Berry, Ana M Valdes, David A Drew, Francesco Asnicar, Mohsen Mazidi, Jonathan Wolf, Joan Capdevila, George Hadjigeorgiou, Richard Davies, Haya Al Khatib, et al. Human postprandial responses to food and potential for precision nutrition. *Nature medicine*, 26(6):964–973, 2020.
- [4] QingXiang Bian, Azizan As' arry, XiangGuo Cong, Khairil Anas bin Md Rezali, and Raja Mohd Kamil bin Raja Ahmad. A hybrid transformer-lstm model apply to glucose prediction. *PLoS One*, 19(9):e0310084, 2024.
- [5] Julian Brummer, Christina Glasbrenner, Sieglinde Hechenbichler Figueroa, Karsten Koehler, and Christoph Höchsmann. Continuous glucose monitoring for automatic real-time assessment of eating events and nutrition: a scoping review. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, 10:1308348, 2024.

- [6] Fergus J Cameron, Susan M Donath, and Peter A Baghurst. Measuring glycaemic variation. *Current diabetes reviews*, 6(1):17–26, 2010.
- [7] Juliana Chen, William Berkman, Manal Bardouh, Ching Yan Kammy Ng, and Margaret Allman-Farinelli. The use of a food logging app in the naturalistic setting fails to provide accurate measurements of nutrients and poses usability challenges. *Nutrition*, 57:208–216, 2019.
- [8] Beyza Cinar, Louisa van den Boom, and Maria Maleshkova. Review of machine learning models in short-and long-term glucose forecasting and hypoglycemia classification. *Informatics in Medicine Unlocked*, page 101723, 2025.
- [9] Pooja M Desai, Elliot G Mitchell, Maria L Hwang, Matthew E Levine, David J Albers, and Lena Mamykina. Personal health oracle: Explorations of personalized predictions in diabetes self-management. In *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, pages 1–13, 2019.
- [10] Stephanie N DuBose, Zoey Li, Jennifer L Sherr, Roy W Beck, William V Tamborlane, and Viral N Shah. Effect of exercise and meals on continuous glucose monitor data in healthy individuals without diabetes. *Journal of Diabetes Science and Technology*, 15(3):593–599, 2021.
- [11] Giuseppe Fico, Liss Hernández, Jorge Cancela, Miguel María Isabel, Andrea Facchinetti, Chiara Fabris, Rafael Gabriel, Claudio Cobelli, and María Teresa Arredondo Waldmeyer. Exploring the frequency domain of continuous glucose monitoring signals to improve characterization of glucose variability and of diabetic profiles. *Journal of diabetes science and technology*, 11(4):773–779, 2017.
- [12] Guido Freckmann, Sebastian Schauer, Anne Beltzer, Delia Waldenmaier, Sina Buck, Annette Baumstark, Nina Jendrike, Manuela Link, Eva Zschornack, Cornelia Haug, et al. Continuous glucose profiles in healthy people with fixed meal times and under everyday life conditions. *Journal of diabetes science and technology*, 18(2):407–413, 2024.

- [13] Eleni I Georga, Vasilios C Protopappas, Diego Ardigo, Demosthenes Polyzos, and Dimitrios I Fotiadis. A glucose model based on support vector regression for the prediction of hypoglycemic events under free-living conditions. *Diabetes technology & therapeutics*, 15(8):634–643, 2013.
- [14] María González-Rodríguez, Marcos Pazos-Couselo, José M García-López, Santiago Rodríguez-Segade, Javier Rodríguez-García, Carmen Túnnez-Bastida, and Francisco Gude. Postprandial glycemic response in a non-diabetic adult population: the effect of nutrients is different between men and women. *Nutrition & metabolism*, 16(1):46, 2019.
- [15] Roman Holzer, Wilhelm Bloch, and Christian Brinkmann. Continuous glucose monitoring in healthy adults—possible applications in health care, wellness, and sports. *Sensors*, 22(5):2030, 2022.
- [16] Paul RE Jarvis, Jessica L Cardin, Pamela M Nisevich-Bede, and James P McCarter. Continuous glucose monitoring in a healthy population: understanding the post-prandial glycemic response in individuals without diabetes mellitus. *Metabolism*, 146:155640, 2023.
- [17] Donggeun Kim and Taesup Kim. Missing modality prediction for unpaired multi-modal learning via joint embedding of unimodal models. In *European Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 171–187. Springer, 2024.
- [18] David C Klonoff, Kevin T Nguyen, Nicole Y Xu, Alberto Gutierrez, Juan C Espinoza, and Alaina P Vidmar. Use of continuous glucose monitors by people without diabetes: an idea whose time has come? *Journal of diabetes science and technology*, 17(6):1686–1697, 2023.
- [19] Sang-Min Lee, Dae-Yeon Kim, and Jiyoung Woo. Glucose transformer: Forecasting glucose level and events of hyperglycemia and hypoglycemia. *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, 27(3):1600–1611, 2023.

- [20] Kezhi Li, John Daniels, Chengyuan Liu, Pau Herrero, and Pantelis Georgiou. Convolutional recurrent neural networks for glucose prediction. *IEEE journal of biomedical and health informatics*, 24(2):603–613, 2019.
- [21] Kui Liu, Linyi Li, Yifei Ma, Jun Jiang, Zhenhua Liu, Zichen Ye, Shuang Liu, Chen Pu, Changsheng Chen, and Yi Wan. Machine learning models for blood glucose level prediction in patients with diabetes mellitus: systematic review and network meta-analysis. *JMIR medical informatics*, 11(1):e47833, 2023.
- [22] Yurun Lu, Dan Liu, Zhongming Liang, Rui Liu, Pei Chen, Yitong Liu, Jiachen Li, Zhanying Feng, Lei M Li, Bin Sheng, et al. A pretrained transformer model for decoding individual glucose dynamics from continuous glucose monitoring data. *National Science Review*, 12(5):nwaf039, 2025.
- [23] Guy Lutsker, Gal Sapir, Smadar Shilo, Jordi Merino, Anastasia Godneva, Jerry R Greenfield, Dorit Samocha-Bonet, Raja Dhir, Francisco Gude, Shie Mannor, et al. A foundation model for continuous glucose monitoring data. *Nature*, pages 1–9, 2026.
- [24] Mengmeng Ma, Jian Ren, Long Zhao, Sergey Tulyakov, Cathy Wu, and Xi Peng. Smil: Multimodal learning with severely missing modality. In *Proceedings of the AAAI conference on artificial intelligence*, volume 35, pages 2302–2310, 2021.
- [25] Cindy Marling and Razvan Bunescu. The ohiot1dm dataset for blood glucose level prediction: Update 2020. In *CEUR workshop proceedings*, volume 2675, page 71, 2020.
- [26] Helena Mendes-Soares, Tali Raveh-Sadka, Shahar Azulay, Kim Edens, Yatir Ben-Shlomo, Yossi Cohen, Tal Ofek, Davidi Bachrach, Josh Stevens, Dorin Colibaseanu, et al. Assessment of a personalized approach to predicting postprandial glycemic responses to food among individuals without diabetes. *JAMA network open*, 2(2):e188102–e188102, 2019.

- [27] Diane C Mitchell, Feon W Cheng, Christopher D Still, and Gordon L Jensen. A validation of automated self-administered 24-hour dietary recalls (asa24) relative to interviewer-administered recalls using the nutrition data system for research (ndsr). *The FASEB Journal*, 30:43–3, 2016.
- [28] Ali Mohebbi, Alexander R Johansen, Nicklas Hansen, Peter E Christensen, Jens M Tarp, Morten L Jensen, Henrik Bengtsson, and Morten Mørup. Short term blood glucose prediction based on continuous glucose monitoring data. In *2020 42nd annual international conference of the IEEE engineering in medicine & biology society (EMBC)*, pages 5140–5145. IEEE, 2020.
- [29] Carmen Pérez-Gandía, Andrea Facchinetti, Giovanni Sparacino, Claudio Cobelli, EJ Gómez, M Rigla, Alberto De Leiva, and ME Hernando. Artificial neural network algorithm for online glucose prediction from continuous glucose monitoring. *Diabetes technology & therapeutics*, 12(1):81–88, 2010.
- [30] Goran Petrovski, Judith Campbell, Maheen Pasha, Emma Day, Khalid Hussain, Amel Khalifa, and Tim van den Heuvel. Simplified meal announcement versus precise carbohydrate counting in adolescents with type 1 diabetes using the minimized 780g advanced hybrid closed loop system: a randomized controlled trial comparing glucose control. *Diabetes Care*, 46(3):544–550, 2023.
- [31] Francesco Prendin, Simone Del Favero, Martina Vettoretti, Giovanni Sparacino, and Andrea Facchinetti. Forecasting of glucose levels and hypoglycemic events: head-to-head comparison of linear and nonlinear data-driven algorithms based on continuous glucose monitoring data only. *Sensors*, 21(5):1647, 2021.
- [32] Md Fazle Rabby, Yazhou Tu, Md Imran Hossen, Insup Lee, Anthony S Maida, and Xiali Hei. Stacked lstm based deep recurrent neural network with kalman smoothing for blood glucose prediction. *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*, 21(1):101, 2021.
- [33] Michele N Ravelli and Dale A Schoeller. Traditional self-reported dietary instru-

- ments are prone to inaccuracies and new approaches are needed. *Frontiers in nutrition*, 7:90, 2020.
- [34] Jaques Reifman, Srinivasan Rajaraman, Andrei Gribok, and W Kenneth Ward. Predictive monitoring for improved management of glucose levels. *Journal of diabetes science and technology*, 1(4):478–486, 2007.
- [35] Renat Sergazinov, Mohammadreza Armandpour, and Irina Gaynanova. Gluformer: Transformer-based personalized glucose forecasting with uncertainty quantification. In *ICASSP 2023-2023 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, pages 1–5. IEEE, 2023.
- [36] F John Service, George D Molnar, John W Rosevear, Eugene Ackerman, Lael C Gatewood, and William F Taylor. Mean amplitude of glycemic excursions, a measure of diabetic instability. *Diabetes*, 19(9):644–655, 1970.
- [37] Giovanni Sparacino, Francesca Zanderigo, Stefano Corazza, Alberto Maran, Andrea Facchinetti, and Claudio Cobelli. Glucose concentration can be predicted ahead in time from continuous glucose monitoring sensor time-series. *IEEE Transactions on biomedical engineering*, 54(5):931–937, 2007.
- [38] Greta Lee Splansky, Diane Corey, Qiong Yang, Larry D. Atwood, L. Adrienne Cupples, Emelia J. Benjamin, Ralph B. D’Agostino, Caroline S. Fox, Martin G. Larson, Joanne M. Murabito, Christopher J. O’Donnell, Ramachandran S. Vasan, Philip A. Wolf, and Daniel Levy. The third generation cohort of the national heart, lung, and blood institute’s framingham heart study: Design, recruitment, and initial examination. *American Journal of Epidemiology*, 165(11):1328–1335, June 2007.
- [39] Giorgia Tascini, Maria Giulia Berio, Laura Cerquiglini, Elisa Santi, Giulia Mancini, Francesco Rogari, Giada Toni, and Susanna Esposito. Carbohydrate counting in children and adolescents with type 1 diabetes. *Nutrients*, 10(1):109, 2018.

- [40] Félix Tena, Oscar Garnica, Juan Lanchares, and Jose Ignacio Hidalgo. Ensemble models of cutting-edge deep neural networks for blood glucose prediction in patients with diabetes. *Sensors*, 21(21):7090, 2021.
- [41] Kamuran Turksoy, Sediqeh Samadi, Jianyuan Feng, Elizabeth Littlejohn, Laurie Quinn, and Ali Cinar. Meal detection in patients with type 1 diabetes: a new module for the multivariable adaptive artificial pancreas control system. *IEEE journal of biomedical and health informatics*, 20(1):47–54, 2015.
- [42] Gabrielle M Turner-McGrievy, Caroline Glagola Dunn, Sara Wilcox, Alycia K Boutté, Brent Hutto, Adam Hoover, and Eric Muth. Defining adherence to mobile dietary self-monitoring and assessing tracking over time: tracking at least two eating occasions per day is best marker of adherence within two different mobile health randomized weight loss interventions. *Journal of the Academy of Nutrition and Dietetics*, 119(9):1516–1524, 2019.
- [43] Nichole S Tyler and Peter G Jacobs. Artificial intelligence in decision support systems for type 1 diabetes. *Sensors*, 20(11):3214, 2020.
- [44] US Food and Drug Administration. Fda clears first over-the-counter continuous glucose monitor, March 2024. Press announcement.
- [45] Willem J van den Brink, Tim J van den Broek, Salvator Palmisano, Suzan Wopereis, and Iris M de Hoogh. Digital biomarkers for personalized nutrition: predicting meal moments and interstitial glucose with non-invasive, wearable technologies. *Nutrients*, 14(21):4465, 2022.
- [46] Hu Wang, Yuanhong Chen, Congbo Ma, Jodie Avery, Louise Hull, and Gustavo Carneiro. Multi-modal learning with missing modality via shared-specific feature modelling. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 15878–15887, 2023.
- [47] Renjie Wu, Hu Wang, Hsiang-Ting Chen, and Gustavo Carneiro. Deep multimodal

- learning with missing modality: A survey. *Transactions on Machine Learning Research*, 2026. Survey Certification.
- [48] Jinyu Xie and Qian Wang. Benchmarking machine learning algorithms on blood glucose prediction for type i diabetes in comparison with classical time-series models. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, 67(11):3101–3124, 2020.
- [49] Yuewei Xue, Shaopeng Guan, and Wanhai Jia. Bgformer: an improved informer model to enhance blood glucose prediction. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, 157:104715, 2024.
- [50] Jun Yang, Lei Li, Yimeng Shi, and Xiaolei Xie. An arima model with adaptive orders for predicting blood glucose concentrations and hypoglycemia. *IEEE journal of biomedical and health informatics*, 23(3):1251–1260, 2018.
- [51] Ashkan Dehghani Zahedani, Tracey McLaughlin, Arvind Veluvali, Nima Aghaeepour, Amir Hosseinian, Saransh Agarwal, Jingyi Ruan, Shital Tripathi, Mark Woodward, Noosheen Hashemi, et al. Digital health application integrating wearable data and behavioral patterns improves metabolic health. *NPJ digital medicine*, 6(1):216, 2023.
- [52] Chiara Zecchin, Andrea Facchinetti, Giovanni Sparacino, and Claudio Cobelli. How much is short-term glucose prediction in type 1 diabetes improved by adding insulin delivery and meal content information to cgm data? a proof-of-concept study. *Journal of diabetes science and technology*, 10(5):1149–1160, 2016.
- [53] Chiara Zecchin, Andrea Facchinetti, Giovanni Sparacino, Giuseppe De Nicolao, and Claudio Cobelli. Neural network incorporating meal information improves accuracy of short-time prediction of glucose concentration. *IEEE transactions on biomedical engineering*, 59(6):1550–1560, 2012.
- [54] David Zeevi, Tal Korem, Niv Zmora, David Israeli, Daphna Rothschild, Adina Weinberger, Orly Ben-Yacov, Dar Lador, Tali Avnit-Sagi, Maya Lotan-Pompan,

- et al. Personalized nutrition by prediction of glycemic responses. *Cell*, 163(5):1079–1094, 2015.
- [55] Yunhua Zhang, Hazel Doughty, and Cees Snoek. Learning unseen modality interaction. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 36:54716–54726, 2023.
- [56] Taiyu Zhu, Lei Kuang, Chengzhe Piao, Junming Zeng, Kezhi Li, and Pantelis Georgiou. Population-specific glucose prediction in diabetes care with transformer-based deep learning on the edge. *IEEE transactions on biomedical circuits and systems*, 18(2):236–246, 2024.
- [57] Taiyu Zhu, Kezhi Li, Jianwei Chen, Pau Herrero, and Pantelis Georgiou. Dilated recurrent neural networks for glucose forecasting in type 1 diabetes. *Journal of Healthcare Informatics Research*, 4(3):308–324, 2020.
- [58] Katrin Zieseimer, Laura Maria König, Carol Jo Boushey, Karoline Villinger, Deborah Ronja Wahl, Simon Butscher, Jens Müller, Harald Reiterer, Harald Thomas Schupp, and Britta Renner. Occurrence of and reasons for “missing events” in mobile dietary assessments: results from three event-based ecological momentary assessment studies. *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, 8(10):e15430, 2020.